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lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
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+639543906965

Quim B. Miolata

Assistant Professor, AB English Language Department
Agusan del Sur State University
Bunawan, Agusan del Sur, Philippines
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The Tree with the Golden Leaves

In the midst of a lovely wood,
Two trees, as I knew, stoutly stood
One shone with leaves of shining gold,
The other stood with branches old.

One looked like a star, so clear, so bright;
While one was ugly to the sight.
And one was proud of its splendor,
As other trees to him adore!

At the tree with the ugly leaves,
The other laughed and proudly said:
"We are truly Nature's pleasure,
But look, am I not more superior?"

But then there came a man one morn,
With eager eyes, both cold and worn.
He saw the gold; his greed grew wide
With axe in hand, he struck with pride.

The splendid tree, in pain, did cry,
As golden leaves went drifting by.
The axe came down; its roots gave way,
Its grandeur faded into gray.

Before it takes its final breath,
To the ugly tree it cried and said:
"Therefore, my friend, remember this,
And tell this to the other trees:

May this lesson take its flight
Not every shining thing lasts the night.
Those who are proud of wealth and fame
Indeed are fools, more than insane".